

Coastal Changes in the Perspective of Long Term Evolution of an Estuary : Hugli, West Bengal, India

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ABSTRACT

Set in the western edge of the abandoned and eroding western Ganga-Brahmaputra delta, the Hugli is a flood dominated macrotidal estuary and is a sediment sink. Comparative study of maps and images between 1851-55 and 1997 reveals that while progressive accretion or cyclic accretion and erosion characterise its non-reclaimed tidal islets, mainly erosion predominates in the reclaimed islands and estuary margins. Dredging and embankment repairing are regularly needed to sustain its navigational channels and to prevent bank erosion.

For maintenance of morphological steady state, length of a resonant macrotidal estuary, like the Hugli, tends to equal 25 per cent of the wavelength of the tide entering into it. The tidal wavelength, in turn, depends critically upon the mean depth of the estuary - any alteration of which throws the estuary out of equilibrium. The hydrographic charts of 1904-05 and 1988-92 indicate that this equals 17 per cent in the Hugli, explaining the coastal erosion and in-channel siltation seen there.

A rise in the future sea level will lead to an increase in the mean depth of the estuary and remove it even further from the steady state condition. In view of this, controlled retreat from its reclaimed islands and marginal areas and relocation of the resident population should be seriously considered for wetland restoration. These, however, are not easy tasks because of the high population of interior areas.

Key words : Estuary, Equilibrium, Cyclic and secular changes, Erosion, Reclamation.

INTRODUCTION

A number of criteria can be used to define an estuary, the tidal mouth of a large river. The principal among these are salinity penetration (Pritchard, 1967), morphological constriction (Hawkins, 1979) and limit of tidal propagation into the river (Fairbridge, 1980). The Hugli is the westernmost distributary of the Ganga-Brahmaputra delta complex. The net terrestrial sediment discharge of the river has been variously estimated from $473 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$ (Bandyopadhyay and Bandyopadhyay, 1996) to $616 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$ (Sengupta et al. 1989). The landward limit of its estuarine reach, defined on the basis of upstream limit of saltwater incursion (Sengupta et al. 1989) is at Diamond Harbour (Hospital Point), about 70 km from its mouth that open into the Bay of Bengal (Fig.1). This is also the place where the horizontal convergence of the estuary margins ceases to be significant and the maximum tidal range (5 m) of this resonant macrotidal estuary is achieved. Morphologically, the Hugli estuary is clearly divided into mutually evasive flood-dominated and ebb-dominated pathways (Roy, 1969) with linear tidal sand ridges occupying the regions in between. At the mouth of its main branch, west of Sagar island (Fig.1), the maximum flood and ebb discharges amount to $2.6 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $1.09 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively (Mcdowell and O'Connor, 1977, p.10). The duration of flood tide is only about 3 hours in a 12.4 hour tidal cycle, setting up flood velocities in the range of $2-3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (Sanyal and Chatterjee, 1995) and, in general, a net landward movement of sediments

(Ghotankar, 1972) due to the time-velocity asymmetry in tidal propagation. These features of the Hugli are common to many macrotidal estuaries of the world (Wells, 1995).

The history of deterioration of the Bhagirathi-Hugli system during the last few centuries is well known (Sherwill, 1858; Reaks, 1919; Bagchi, 1944; Morgan and McIntire, 1959; Basu and Chakraborty, 1972). The river's lower course is now chiefly maintained by the tides and its right bank tributaries apart from the 1975 Farakka barrage scheme that diverts certain amount of water from the Ganga. The maximum possible discharge of $1,135 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($40,000 \text{ ft}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) from the barrage can increase the ebb flux at the sea face to only about 2 per cent - hardly influencing the flow conditions of the estuary (Roy, 1969). During the dry period between January and May, available augmentation remains much lower than the maximum possible discharge (Islam, 1987, p.182). Consequently, while the Farakka project did improve navigability of the upper parts of the Hugli, it had no apparent effect on the estuarine reach of the river (Sanyal and Chakrabarti, 1995).

The Hugli estuary, being the passage to the ports of Haldiya and Calcutta, is the most important maritime lifeline of the economies of eastern India, Nepal and Bhutan. At the same time, a high rate of sedimentation and continuous changes in bathymetry (Fig.2) made it

Fig.1 The Hugli estuary. All spot heights and depths have reference to High Water Level Sprigs (HWLS). GI=Ghoramara Island. (Based on geometrically rectified IRS-1B LISS-2 FCC of 14 Feb.,1992 and Calcutta Port Trust chart of 1992. Spot heights are from SoI map nos.79B/4, 79C/1 & 79C/2 of 1967-69. Tidal ranges (springs) are from SoI, (1992).

Fig.2 Shifting positions of the main navigational channels of the Hugli estuary between 1768 and 1997. (Source : 1768-1918: Reaks 1919; 1945: Roy, 1969; 1970: Chakrabarti and Sen, 1972; 1997: Calcutta Port Trust. Base map: IRS-1C LISS-3 Geocoded FCC nos. 79B04, 79C01 and 79C02 of 6 January, 1997).

one of the world's most difficult rivers to navigate (Mistry, 1972; McDowell, 1995). Some 14×10^6 m³ of sediments are dredged annually from the estuary to keep its navigational channels open (Sanyal and Chakrabarti, 1995). Reclamation of some of the estuary's tidal islets and marginal areas, by placing low-tech earthen embankments, was started from the early 19th century (O'Malley, 1914; Ascoli, 1921; Pargiter, 1934; Lahiri, 1936). At present, farmlands, supporting a population density of more than 750 persons per km², largely replaced the once-teeming mangroves along nearly the entire stretch of its margins and in the tidal islands of Sagar and Ghoramara (Plate 1 & Fig.1). Besides the port and shipping authorities, this resident population is also inseparably linked to the changing planform of the estuary.

PREVIOUS WORKS

Initial reports on coastline changes (erosion) in the Hugli estuary includes Anon (1841), Wilson (1846), Hunter (1875) and O'Malley (1914) - all dealing with Sagar, the largest island of the estuary. In the later years, a number of contributions were made on the long term bathymetric evolution of the estuary since the middle of the 19th century or even earlier (Reaks, 1919; Hiranandani and Ghotankar, 1961; Roy, 1969; McDowell and O'Connor, 1977; Bhattacharya, 1973, besides the unpublished reports of the Hydraulic Study Department, Calcutta Port Trust). Some work on its morphological steady state was also carried out by Wright et al., (1973). However, although many of the reclaimed areas of the estuary are under active erosion for decades

Plate-1 Setting of the Hugli estuary in the western Ganga-Brahmaputra delta. The estuaries to its east have no connection with the up-country rivers. The light grey tint of the coastal delta denotes Sundarban mangroves (Landsat-1 MSS image of 21 February, 1973).

Plate-3 Eroding marginal earthen embankment along the Baratala branch of the Hugli in the northern tip of Sagar island (Kachuberiya). Embankments like these require extensive yearly maintenance.

Plate-2 Time series photos from the seafacing southeastern Sagar island showing gradual erosion of a coastal village (Shibpur), a scene common to the reclaimed areas of the estuary.

(Plate 2 & 3) (Chakrabarti, 1991, 1995a; Bandyopadhyay et al., 1993; Paul, 1996; Bandyopadhyay, 1997) little work has been done to record their evolutionary history and to specifically address the problem of coastal erosion. Recent works on these areas by Kumar et al., (1994) and Prithviraj et al., (1995) covered a relatively short span of about 25 years from 1967-69 (year of survey, Survey of India's latest topomaps) upto 1991 (1:250,000 IRS-1A LISS-1 image) and 1992 (IRS-1A LISS-2 data) respectively. They did not attempt, however, to correlate the trend of evolution to any specific cause.

With this background, the present article attempts to look into the problem of coastal erosion in the Hugli estuary in two parts. Firstly, by recording the patterns of changes in the area and configuration of individual islands and estuary margins and, secondly, by correlating the observed patterns to adjustments of the estuary for achieving morphological steady state.

PATTERNS OF CHANGE

Coastal changes : materials and methods

A coastline is generally defined as the landward limit of sea water during the high spring tides under normal (i.e. not stormy) conditions (Bird, 1985). Comparing multidated maps, charts, aerial photos and satellite images to evaluate long term coastline changes is a useful world wide practice. The results of such works are generally expressed in terms of areal or linear measurements over a specific time interval, determined from the dates of the materials used (Carr, 1962, 1980; DeBoer and Carr, 1969; Bird, 1985; Cooke and Doorncamp, 1989; Dugdale, 1990). However, as Bird

(1985) recognised, defining the limit of spring tides is a matter of interpretation and often a problem by itself. This is intrinsic to most studies involving coastline shifts images, coastlines are generally measured with reference to the seaward limits of frontal dunes, backshore vegetation or marginal embankments.

Details of the materials studied for the present work are given in Table 1. These materials came in many different sizes and had to be converted to a standard scale (in this case 1:253,440), for diagrammatic reproduction (Fig.3). An *Optomech-011* optical pantagraph (magnification range : 0.25x to 4.5x) and a *Korestat A-31* photocopier (magnification range : 0.4 x to 2x) were used for all the reduction jobs. The graticules and reasonably permanent cultural features like roads and embankments were used as the references for matching the maps and images with one another. The distortions in the final products, which are inherent to the method employed (Carr, 1962), are likely to be insignificant here due to the fact that the

maps and images were reduced, rather than enlarged, in scale.

Among the various methods for aerial measurements, polar planimeters are by far the most effective (Gardiner, 1990). Consequently, in this work a *Sokkia Placom KP-90N* digital planimeter was used to calculate the supratidal areas enclosed by the high spring tide line directly from the original materials.

Table 1 Changes in the area of the tidal islets of the Hugli estuary: data source

Producing authority	Details of the map/chart/image	Year of survey/Date of pass	Scale
Sol	Map no.121 of Atlas of India	1851-55	1:253,440
Sol	Map no.482 -S.00	1882-83	1:253,440
RSD	River Hugli : Kulpi to Lower Gasper Light Vessel	1903-04	1:72,625
RSD	River Hooghly: Calcutta to Saugor	1904-05	1:80,724
Sol	Map no.79B/4	1922-23	1:63,360
Sol	Map no.79C/1	1922-23	1:63,360
Sol	Map no.79C/2	1922-23	1:63,360
CPC	River Hooghly	1938	1:145,728
Sol	Map no.79C/2	1942	1:63,360
Sol	Map no.79B/4	1967-68	1:50,000
Sol	Map no.79C/1	1967-68	1:50,000
Sol	Map no.79C/2	1968-69	1:50,000
Sol	Aerial photomosaic (68 photos in 9 runs)	6 Mar 1977	1:50,000
CPT	River Hugli	1992	1:100,000
NRSA	IRS-1C, LISS -3 Geocoded FCC no.79B04	6 January 1997	1:50,000
NRSA	IRS-1C, LISS -3 Geocoded FCC no.79C01	6 January 1997	1:50,000
NRSA	IRS-1C, LISS-3 Geocoded FCC no.79C02	6 January 1997	1:50,000

Sol: Survey of India, RSD: River Survey Department, CPC: Calcutta Port Comissioners
CPT: Calcutta Port Trust, NRSA: National Remote Sensing Agency.

Fig.3 Changes in the tidal islands of the Hugli estuary between 1851-55 and 1997. Island names (as in the original maps/charts): AM = Agnimari, BF = Bedford, CS = Chuksar, CL = Cromellin or Chromelian, ES = Edmonstone, GM = Ghoramara, GT = Gabtala, HD = Haldiya, JB = Jambu, KM = Kakramari, KP = Korapara, LC = Lohachara, LS = Lash's, NC = Nayachara, NW = New, SB = Suparbhangra, SG = Sagar, SP = Shikarpur (Source : Refer to Table 1 by years.)

All inter-tidal areas, including that of intra-island creeks, were not considered. Small islands, that accreted very close to the bank of the estuary and subsequently merged with it, were also not considered for area estimations. There were four such instances in the estuary area : Haldia (south of Haldi confluence, not to be confused with the Haldia island that emerged around 1903-05),

Rangafalla-East, Rangafalla-West (both south of Kulpi) and Kabasgadi (west of Kakdwip).

Coastal changes : results

The results obtained from the comparative study of the maps, charts and images of the estuary are summarised in Fig.3, 4 & 5 and in Table 2. As they show the changes in the individual island areas for the last 143 years like snapshots of a continuum, a few trends become discernible:

* The largest island of the estuary, the reclaimed Sagar, showed progressive erosion through most of the period (barring 1938-42—1967-69), influencing the net results.

* The second largest island of the estuary, the non-reclaimed Nayachara, showed progressive accretion since its re-emergence (in 1948: T.Sanyal, pers. com.), also influencing the net results.

* Most other islands, mostly non-reclaimed, showed cyclic accretion and erosion.

* As a whole, an approximate 70-year cycle (from 1851-55 to 1922-23 and from 1922-23 to 1997) of net growth and dissipation of total area, incorporating all islands, is indicated.

* Total area of the islands never varied more than $\pm 4.33\%$ of 272.96 km².

* Total number of islands fluctuated through the years but showed a clearly increasing trend.

* Lastly, from the overall view provided by Fig.5, it is indicated that the areas subjected to erosion between 1904-05 and 1992 were mostly reclaimed stretches of the estuary where marginal embankments were placed while accretion took place mostly in the non-reclaimed regions.

CAUSES OF CHANGE

The region

The course and rate of delta building mostly depend on the relative dominance of the accretional fluvial processes and the erosive tidal and marine processes (Reading and Collinson, 1996). Growth of

deltas tends to be cyclic between prograding and destructive phases that involve some or all of the delta lobes (Boggs, 1987). As connoted by Fig.6, the Ganga-Brahmaputra delta coastline west of the Haringhata estuary (in Bangladesh) is retrograding for more than a century and half mainly due to the gradual abandonment of its sediment replenishing western distributaries (Oldham, 1870; Oldham, 1893; Chakrabarti, 1995b) and off-shore interception and transportation of sediments to the deep-sea Bengal fan by the Swatch of No Ground submarine canyon (Sherwill, 1858, Kuehl et al., 1989). The delta is also prone to autocompaction-related subsidence (Fawcus, 1927; Morgon and McIntire, 1959, Alam, 1989; Das and Bhattacharya, 1994) and highly destructive tropical cyclones (IMD, 1979). Rapid erosion of the sea facing southern coastline of the Hugli estuary fits well into this regional model. The erosion of the mangrove-dominated reaches of this part of the coast also confirms that coastal retrogradation here is not linked to deforestation (Bandyopadhyay and Bandyopadhyay, 1996).

On the other hand, the periodic accretional phases in an overall erosional scene of the delta and the emergence and submergence of the small islands along its southern periphery can be ascribed to reworking of the erosional products and other sediments by the delta's high energy environment. This is common in many eroding world deltas such as the Nile (Carter, 1988, p.483) and does not indicate subaerial progradation although sometimes suggested (e.g. by Ahmad, 1972; Bird, 1985; Chattopadhyay, 1985; Basu and Sen, 1994). However, specially off the Hugli estuary, there are indications for slow progradation of the subaqueous part of the delta (Reaks, 1919; Hiranandani and Ghotankar, 1961).

The Estuary :

Operation of cycles of accretion and erosion

The continuous widening of the Baratala branch of the estuary (minimum width: 1.1 km in 1851-55 and 3.0 km in 1997) might be a connotation for the detachment of Sagar from its eastern margin. This makes the reclaimed Sagar and Ghoramara (the latter formed a part of Sagar before 1904-05 : see Fig.2) somewhat different from other islands of the estuary which are the exposed parts of the linear tidal sand ridges that line the estuary floor and are closely linked to the cyclic changes and migrations of the ridges themselves. Reclamation

Table 2 Changes in the area of the tidal islets of the Hugli estuary : results

Source ¹	SoI	SoI	RSD	RSD	SoI	CPC&SoI	SoI	SoI	NRSA
Year	1851-55	1882-83	1903-04	1904-05	1922-23	1938&42	1967-69	1977	1997
Unnamed island (northeast of Nayachara)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.22 (100%)
Haldiya/Agnimari/ Nayachara ²	-	-	0.22 (0.49%)	0.21 (0.47%)	submerged	submerged	15.88 (35.38%)	31.17 (69.45%)	45.59 (100%)
Ghoramara (inch.Lash's)	-	-	-	9.70 (45.28%)	21.42 (100%)	8.68 (87.21%)	8.47 (46.51%)	7.07 (33.01%)	5.41 (25.23%)
Gabtala/Bedford/ Suparbhangra	-	1.41 (16.52%)	2.04 (23.29%)	2.24 (26.26%)	8.53 (100%)	8.25 (96.72%)	1.93 (22.6%)	sub- merged	sub- merged
Korapara/Lohachara	-	3.21 (41.00%)	1.44 (18.39%)	1.01 (12.90%)	7.48 (95.53%)	7.83 (100%)	4.05 (51.72%)	3.69 (41.13%)	submerged
Saugor / Sagar	284.55 (100%)	269.67 (94.77%)	255.25 (89.70%)	245.48 (86.27%)	240.12 (84.39%)	221.06 (77.69%)	223.56 (78.57%)	220.41 (77.46%)	221.12 (77.71%)
Shikarpur-North	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.25 (100%)	1.63 (72.44%)	0.6 (26.67%)
Shikarpur-South	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.75 (77.32%)	1.03 (100%)
Crommellin/Chromelian/ Kakramari	-	-	0.37 (22.84%)	0.36 (22.22%)	1.19 (73.46%)	submerged	1.23 (75.92%)	1.62 (100%)	0.48 (29.63%)
Edmonstone/Jambu	-	-	0.52 (5.95%)	0.52 (5.95%)	0.66 (7.55%)	submerged	8.74 (100%)	7.72 (88.33%)	5.03 (57.55%)
New	-	-	1.31 (16.99%)	1.20 (15.56%)	5.36 (69.52%)	7.71 (100%)	sub- merged	sub- merged	sub- merged
Chuksar	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.11 (100%)	1.00 (90.09%)	0.99 (89.19%)
ALL ISLANDS	284.55 (99.93%)	274.29 (96.32%)	261.15 (91.71%)	260.90 (91.62%)	284.76 (100%)	253.53 (89.03%)	267.22 (93.84%)	275.06 (96.59%)	280.47 (98.49%)

1. See Table 1 for details

2. Name of a given island changes from map to map.

of Sagar, initiated from 1811 (Chapman, 1869), might have prevented operation of this nature cycle, which could have started an accretionary phase in the island. There are several evidences that human interference often leads to disruption of natural cycles in a coastal system (Pethick, 1992).

An island group on the tidal sand ridge of Sagar Sand, in the outer estuary, perhaps best illustrates how repetitive can an accretion-erosion cycle be. Reaks (1919, p.37-38) described that, 'according to Horsburgh', the island of Edmonstone accreted in 1817 from an incipient intertidal shoal to a 3.2 km long and 0.8 km wide area, where a house for the harbour pilots was constructed in 1825. A cyclone in 1833 divided the island

islet, the New, simultaneously appeared further south (Reaks, 1919). About 34 years later, Edmonstone got divided again and, bringing another phase to end, once again dissipated within the next decade. Meanwhile, New grew to its maximum recorded size of 7.71 km² (Fig.3). Within the subsequent 36 years, while Edmonstone (now called Jambu), well into the third cycle of existence, re-emerged and reached its largest recorded size of 8.74 km², New washed away altogether. Since that time (1968-69), Jambu again has started to diminish in size while, as the 1997 satellite images indicate, New is on the verge of making reappearance. This denotes operation of an approximate 50-year emergence-submergence cycle for both Jambu and New. Reaks (1919) also informed that, on the tidal ridge of Long Sand, where the Chuksar island accreted between

Fig.4 Progressive and cyclic changes in the areas of the individual islands of the Hugli estuary between 1851-55 and 1997 (Based on Table 1).

1942 and 1968-69, fairly vegetated islands used to form and obliterate prior to 1851-55.

None of the islands of the enclosed part of the estuary proper, however, showed comparatively fast cycles of evolution. Finding 'remarkable similarity' between the 1881 and 1967 orientations of the tidal sand ridges and thalwegs of the estuary from Nayachara to Sagar South (Fig.1), Roy (1969) suggested that the movement of the tidal sand ridges of the estuary follows a 90 to 100 year cycle that also causes significant oscillations in the positions of its navigational channels (Fig.2). Comparison between the conditions of the estuary in 1910-11 (30 years since 1881) and the present (30 years since 1967), does indicate some similarity except the present position of the Rangafalla crossing (Fig.1). If Roy's cycle operates, then the Rangafalla channel should start getting closed by southward movement of the Haldiya tidal sand ridge, now exposed as the Nayachara island, within the next few years (See Hiranandani and Ghotankar, 1961 for the 1910-11 planform of the estuary). North of Nayachara, McDowell and O'Connor (1977) described operation of a cycle of similar time interval involving eastward and westward swinging of the estuary margins at the vicinity of Diamond Sand.

Mean depth and morphological steady state of an estuary

Wright et al., (1973) showed that in a morphological steady state, length of a resonant macrotidal estuary (1), like the Hugli, tends to equal a quarter of the tidal wavelength (L) generated in it, that is:

$$1 \rightarrow 0.25 L$$

Length of the tidal wave (which behaves as a shallow water wave in an estuary), in turn, is determined by tidal period (T - a constant in a given locality), gravitational acceleration (g - another constant: 9.81 m sec⁻²) and mean depth of the estuary (D - the only variable) so that they satisfy:

$$L = T \sqrt{gD}$$

Reclamation, by restricting the area of tidal spill through marginal embankments, removes shallow intertidal wetlands from the reach of the estuary and thereby increases its mean depth - which is of critical importance. This throws the estuary out of morphological equilibrium (Fig.7). The estuary then responds by active in-channel sedimentation and bank

Fig.5 Changes in the Hugli estuary between 1904-05 and 1992. Most of the eroded areas are located in the reclaimed parts of the estuary (Based on RSD chart of 1904-05, IRS-1B LISS-2 FCC of 14 Feb., 1992 and CPT chart of 1992). GI = Ghoramara Island

erosion to decrease the mean depth and to restore the steady state condition (Pethick, 1994). Further, the difference in flow of water between a tidal channel and the mangrove wetlands adjacent to it leads to dynamic tidal circulation that maintains the channel depth. Removal of the mangroves disturbs this balance and also results in siltation of the channel (Augustinus, 1995).

It has been seen in one of the previous sections that the Hugli estuary is a sediment sink, necessitating extensive dredging operations to keep its navigational channels open. Erosion of marginal embankments along the reclaimed stretches of the estuary has also been found to be very common. Although these indicate that the estuary must be out of the steady state condition to a large degree, Wright et al. (1973) showed the mean depth (D) and the estuary length / tidal wavelength ratio ($1/L$) of the Hugli to be 5.88 m

Fig.6 Superposed maps and images of various years connote that the coastline of the western Ganga-Brahmaputra delta, except a few localities, is retrograding for nearly past 150 years. (Source : A & B: After Fig. 1 & 6 of Reaks, 1919. C : SoI sheet nos 79C and 79G (both 2nd editions) originally reduced to 1:1,000,000 and Alam, et al. 1990; D : SoI sheet no 79C/2 of various editions and IRS-1C LISS-3 Geocoded FCC of 6 January, 1997-all originally converted to 1:50,000).

Fig.7 Diagrams explaining consequences of reclaiming a macro-tidal estuary. A: Intertidal areas are not reclaimed - estuary is in morphological equilibrium. B: Intertidal areas are reclaimed - mean depth is increased and the estuary is removed from morphological equilibrium. Feedback would include in-channel siltation and erosion of the embankments.

and 0.22 respectively. These figures do not indicate significant deviations from the morphological steady state condition. Wright et al. based their estimates on unspecified hydrographic charts and US Department of Commerce Tide Tables. The Baratala branch of the estuary was not considered. In fact, they used the 1/L ratio of 0.22 to support their main postulation noted at the beginning of this section.

This calls for reinvestigation.

Mean depth and wavelength estimation : materials and methods

The tidal period (T) of the estuary was calculated from Survey of India Tide Tables of 1992 (SoI, 1992) by dividing the number of hours of that year by the number of high tides generated in the same year. This was found to be 12.42 hr or 44712 s.

Details of the bathymetric charts used for the mean depth estimation of the Hugli estuary are given in Table 3. Because the individual depth soundings (d) were equally spaced for a given hydrographic chart, they were first added up and then the sum was divided by the number of soundings (n) to find the mean depth (D). However, in some instances the spacing was comparatively wide over some intertidal shoals. In cases like these, extra sounding points were introduced to match the density of the soundings elsewhere, and were ascribed the mean value found from the existing soundings of that shoal. As the soundings of the intertidal areas are shown as heights above the datum of the charts, they were considered as negative depth (-d) values in mean depth (D) measurement. That is:

$$D = (\Sigma d + \Sigma -d)/n$$

Because the estuary in 1988-92 was covered by two National Hydrographic Office (NHO) and one Calcutta Port Trust (CPT) charts with different scales and density of soundings, mean depths of each of the three charts were found out and, in final estimation, were weighted according to the per cent of area of the estuary they covered (Table 3), to find out the overall mean depth.

As in all charts, the depth soundings used here were based on certain datum levels. The mean depth of a given chart was obviously related to its and not to any tide or sea level. For finding out the mean depth below Mean Low Water Springs (MLWS) or Mean High Water Springs (MHWS), their relationship with the chart datum, generally defined as: 'a plane so low that the tide will but seldom fall below it' (Ingham, 1992, p.10), is very

important (Table 3). This varies by 0.72 m from the mouth to the head of the hypersynchronous Hugli estuary. For example, the MHWS rises 5.22 m, 5.60 m, 5.70 m and 5.94 m above the chart datum of the NHO and CPT charts at about 1 km, 32 km, 44 km and 69 km landwards from the mouth of the estuary respectively (1=70 km). To find out the mean depth below MHWS, these were averaged out and the value (5.615 m) was added to the chart datum. Similarly, to estimate the mean depth below MLWS, 0.873 m was added to the chart datum. In the latter case, soundings of the intertidal areas (Σ -d) were not considered.

Mean depth and tidal wavelength estimation : results

The results of the estimation of mean depth and 1/L ratio of the estuary are shown in Table 4. Pethick (1994) noted that in case of bifurcating estuaries, both of the branches should be considered for depth estimation. Elsewhere he specifically mapped the Hugli estuary along with its Baratala branch (Pethick, 1984). In the present case, however, exclusion or inclusion of the Baratala branch of the estuary did not change the results significantly.

DISCUSSION

It becomes clear from Table 4 that if the MLWS is taken as the datum for mean depth estimations, the level of which is 0.41 m and 0.87 m above the KODS and CD respectively (Table 3), the estuary, with $1 = 0.21 L$, is positioned close to the morphological steady state ($1 \rightarrow 0.25 L$) and closely matches with Wright et al's (1973) figure of $1 = 0.22 L$. The datum of MHWS, on the other hand, takes the intertidal areas of the estuary into consideration, which are of critical significance for estimation of mean depth (Pethick, 1994, 1996). If the MHWS is taken as the datum, the relationship of $1 = 0.17 L$ makes the estuary too deep to be anywhere near the morphological steady state and explains the ground reality to a large extent.

It is interesting to note that there has hardly been any change in the 1/L ratio of the estuary between 1904-05 and 1988-92 although the mean depths, in all the four categories barring one, decreased slightly, as did the length of the estuary, due to constant erosion of the delta face (Table 4). It is possible that 85 years were not enough to allow any noticeable restoration of the estuary's morphological equilibrium. The southern areas of Sagar island and the southernmost parts of the eastern margin of the estuary were not fully reclaimed in 1904-05. (The reclamation of these regions was completed by 1930s).

Table 3 Estimation of length / tidal wavelength ratio of the Hugli : data source

1904-05	River Survey Department (RSD) Chart 'River Hooghly: Calcutta to Saugor'		
	Scale	:	1:80,724
	Number of soundings (n)	:	6537
	Datum of soundings	:	Khidirpur Old Dock Sill (KODS)
	Level of Khidirpur Old Dock Sill (KODS) ¹	:	0.4125 m below Mean Low Water Springs (MLWS) 5.155 m below Mean High Water Springs (MHWS) 2.36 m below Mean Sea Level (MSL) 0.46 m above Chart Datum (CD)
1988-92	1. Naval Hydrographic Office (NHO) Chart no.3013 'Hugli River'		
	Scale	:	1:375,000
	Number of soundings (n)	:	844
	Datum of soundings	:	Chart Datum (CD)
	Coverage of the estuary	:	Northern 33.82%
	2. Naval Hydrographic off (NHO) Chart no.3011 'Hugli River'.		
	Scale	:	1:75,000
	Number of soundings (n)	:	573
	Datum of soundings	:	Chart Datum (CD)
	Coverage of the estuary	:	Southern 51.37% (excl. Baratala branch)
	3. Calcutta Port Trust (CPT) Chart 'Hugli River'		
	Scale	:	1:100,000
	Number of soundings (n)	:	109
	Datum of soundings	:	Chart Datum (CD)
	Coverage of the estuary	:	Southern 14.81% (Baratala branch)
Level of Chart Datum (CD) ¹	:	0.8725 m below Mean Low Water Springs (MLWS) 5.615 m below Mean High Water Springs (MHWS) 2.82 m below Mean Sea Level (MSL) 0.46 m below Khidirpur Old Dock Sill (KODS)	

1. Source : Sol (1992).

Table 4 Estimation of length / tidal wavelength ratio of the Hugli : results

Year	Datum (and part of the estuary considered)	n	D (m)	L (km)	l (km)	L/l
1904-05	MLWS (excluding Baratala branch)	4888	5.61	331.61	70.8	0.21
	MLWS (including Baratala branch)	5352	5.63	332.35	71.7	0.22
	MHWS (excluding Baratala branch)	5973	9.25	425.83	70.8	0.17
	MHWS (including Baratala branch)	6537	9.27	426.38	71.7	0.17
1988-92	MLWS (excluding Baratala branch)	1137	5.49	328.07	70	0.21
	MLWS (including Baratala branch)	1203	5.72	334.82	70	0.21
	MHWS (excluding Baratala branch)	1417	8.96	419.15	70	0.17
	MHWS (including Baratala branch)	1526	8.95	418.91	70	0.17

MLWS=Mean Low Water Springs; MHWS=Mean High Water Springs; n=number of soundings; D=mean depth; L=tidal wavelength; l=estuary length.

Non-inclusion of the shallow intertidal reaches of these areas in the 1904-05 charts might also have affected the results and made the estuary deeper than it actually was.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The accretion and erosion of most of the non-reclaimed tidal islets of the Hugli estuary follow a rhythmic pattern which can be explained by morphological and/or positional changes of the tidal sand ridges of the estuary. This connotes that the rapid accretion of the Nayachara island will probably be followed by an erosional phase in the future. Cycles with operational spans between 50 and 100 years have been suggested in the present work and by other authors (Roy, 1969; McDowell and O'Connor, 1977). However, since these are based on observations in the range of only about 150-200 years, they should be used with caution.

The reclaimed area, specially the large Sagar island and stretches along the banks of the estuary, were subjected to continuous erosion for nearly the last 150

years. An estuary length / tidal wavelength ratio of 0.17 for the Hugli indicates that the erosion might be an upshot of a disturbed morphological equilibrium of the estuary by the process of reclamation itself. It might be argued that erosion was also present in, for example, Sagar island in the late 19th century when some parts of the island still remained non-reclaimed. However, erosion of the partially non-reclaimed Sagar could be a part of the natural cycle of erosion and accretion. Reclamation, apart from contributing to the upsetting of the estuary's steady state condition, might also have prevented an accretional phase of the cycle from setting in.

Any estuary is extremely responsive to increase in the sea level (Dyer, 1995). An accelerated rise of the relative sea level in the Hugli estuary area due to subsidence and global greenhouse warming in near future (Mahtab, 1992; Broadus, 1993) will translate into increased depth of the estuary and remove it even further from the steady state condition. There are now ample evidences from the resonant macrotidal estuaries of the United Kingdom (Pethick, 1994) that removal of embankment and / or wetland restoration do help in alleviating marginal erosion and in improving depths of navigable channels. According to Maddrell (1993), regional removal of embankments showed marked improvement in depths of the previously silted estuary-margin tidal channels in southeastern Bangladesh. In view of this, it seems that controlled retreat from the reclaimed stretches (which mostly consists of farmlands of low economic value) and relocating the resident population in some other areas are the only long term solutions to the problem of erosion of the marginal areas of the Hugli estuary. These are not easy tasks in view of the high population density and growth rate of the region (eg. in Sagar island these figures were 865 persons km⁻² and 3.99 % yr⁻¹ respectively in 1991). On the other hand, costly upgrading of the low-tech estuary-margin embankments to combat rising sea level would only accentuate the coastal squeeze and the resulting feedbacks would worsen the situation even more.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I have received helps and suggestions from Dr. Ashesh Ghatak, Dr. Tapobrata Sanyal and Dr. John Pethick. Computer support was provided by Ms. Nivedita Roy Burman. I wish to thank all of them.

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